

UOT 338.45

INDUSTRY AND ITS DEVELOPMENT STAGES**Nagiyev K.**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15553059>*

Abstract

In the modern stage, industry plays a leading role in terms of the volume and importance of product production necessary for the survival and development of society. The article discusses the factors influencing the emergence and development of industry, as well as its stages of development. It also highlights that, at various stages of historical development, the activities of the first enterprises—arising from the necessity of applying collective labor—and their improvement, the emergence of new forms of labor organization, and the occurrence of scientific-technical and industrial revolutions have led to significant achievements in other areas of material goods production as well.

Keywords: industry, production, labor, economy, commodity

Introduction

Since the population and the economy are elements of a unified social organism, regardless of their form and content, the presence of a sufficiently developed number of physically and mentally capable people and labor potential is a necessary condition for the occurrence and harmonious continuation of the process of social production in all socio-economic formations. People, who act as the main element of the productive forces of any society, also constitute the subjects of production relations, and therefore, when considered as a whole, they significantly influence the development of the productive forces and, consequently, the society itself. In this sense, the prerequisite for the entire history of humanity is, of course, the existence of living human individuals [3, p. 77–78]. Without human labor, the production process can neither begin nor continue. Means and tools of production constitute the productive forces of society only when combined with living human labor [4, p. 57]. The role of labor in the emergence and development of human beings and society has been exceptional. Labor is an eternal natural condition for the development of humans and humanity. This means that labor is not a transient, historical process in human life. From the very beginning, people have interacted with nature to meet their needs, influenced it, and used it for their own purposes [2, p. 13–14]. The formation and development of society began with the activities directed at the collective living of people and the fulfillment of their essential needs. As is known, the sphere of human activity is broad and covers various fields. Regardless of the specific field of activity, people have a common need, which is the demand for material goods. The material goods necessary for human survival are produced in the fields of material production. By material production sectors, we mean the sectors involved in the production of material goods aimed at satisfying both personal and public material and spiritual

needs. These sectors mainly include industry, agriculture, construction, freight transport, production-related communications, public catering, and so on.

Main Part

At the modern stage, industry, as one of the main branches of material production, plays a leading role due to the volume and importance of the goods it produces. The word industry originates from the Latin word *industria*, which means “diligence” or “industriousness”. Industry is a field of material production that, by efficiently using natural resources, produces goods for personal consumption as well as technical and industrial use. It primarily includes sectors such as fuel and energy, mechanical engineering, chemistry, light industry, food production, and others. Industry has gone through several stages of development. As in other fields, its evolution has followed a path from simple to complex.

The initial and simplest form of industry was individual production. Individual production included types such as home industry, craftsmanship, and small-scale industrial goods. This type of production was associated with the activities of various individuals, and particularly in home industry, the producer manufactured goods for their own needs within their household economy. It is evident that this form of production was characteristic of the pre-private enterprise stages and was predominant in societies where subsistence (natural) economies prevailed. A subsistence economy refers to a closed economy — in other words, one that is not connected to markets or trade, where the produced goods are consumed directly by the producers themselves. In a subsistence economy, products do not enter circulation but go directly into the sphere of consumption. This was due to the underdevelopment of the social division of labor. Subsistence economies were

marked by stagnation and weak economic development. Such economies were not dynamic, but rather conservative, stable, and unchanging [1, p.123–124].

With the development of productive forces, individual production also evolved, and a new type—craft and small-scale industrial goods production—emerged during the period marked by the second social division of labor, when craftsmanship separated from agriculture. One of the first industrial sectors to operate based on customer orders was craftsmanship. As craftsmanship developed, the scope of individual production expanded, which in turn led to the emergence of commodity production. A commodity refers to a product manufactured for sale. Craftsmanship is considered part of small-scale commodity production, which was based on individual labor. Unlike the subsistence economy, a commodity economy is a form of production organization in which the goods produced are intended solely for exchange. The commodity economy emerged as the opposite of the subsistence economy. Initially appearing between communities and later within them, the commodity economy gradually subordinated the subsistence economy and eventually replaced it in the economic life of societies [1, p.124].

At a certain stage of historical development, the emergence and deepening of the social division of labor led to the improvement of means of production, making it impossible for them to be operated solely by individual labor. As a result, the application of collective labor became a necessity. Although collective labor existed in societies before private entrepreneurship, it fully matured during the era of free enterprise. The socialization of labor and means of production led to the emergence of social production. The socialization of labor gained momentum during the stages of simple cooperation and manufacturing, and reached a higher level during the stage of large-scale industry. At a certain historical stage of societal development, the first enterprises emerged in the form of simple labor cooperation. Labor cooperation refers to a form in which many individuals work together in the same production process or in different but interrelated production processes. With the advancement of production, the organization of labor was further improved, and simple cooperative enterprises were replaced by manufacturing. Manufacture (from Latin *manus* – hand, and *factura* – to make or produce) refers to labor cooperation based on the division of labor in the creation of a single commodity. Although production was still based on manual labor, workers in manufacturing specialized in specific operations. Manufacturing existed in Western European countries from the late 16th century until the end of the 18th century. However, by the late 18th and early 19th centuries, the technical and industrial revolution led to the emergence of large-scale machine-based industry. The development of this industry gave a strong impulse to the advancement of productive forces. The progress of productive forces and the deepening division of labor

greatly influenced the expansion of technological development, resulting in the emergence and growth of new industrial sectors. For example, during the industrial revolution at the end of the 18th century, light and food industries held the leading position. However, during the scientific and technical revolution in the mid-20th century, heavy industry rapidly developed and took the lead. The scientific and technical revolution brought significant structural changes to industry, leading to the emergence of more progressive sectors. The development of metallurgy, energy, chemical, and other sectors occurred during this period.

Conclusion

Based on the points mentioned above, it can be concluded that several industrial revolutions have taken place throughout different stages of historical development, each playing an exceptional role in the advancement of the economy and other sectors. The first industrial revolution, which occurred in the late 18th and early 19th centuries, led to the mechanization of production, the transition from an agrarian to an industrial economy, urbanization, the invention and integration of steam engines into production, and the emergence of manufactories and factories. The second industrial revolution, which took place from the mid-19th to the early 20th century, was marked by the development of the telephone and telegraph, the rise of the electricity, steel, oil, and automobile industries, and major inventions such as the internal combustion engine. In the mid-20th century, the third industrial revolution—also known as the "Digital Revolution"—occurred, resulting in the automation of production through electronics and technology. The development of electronics and information technologies, particularly the invention and widespread use of computers and the internet, also had a profound impact on economic growth. Currently, the world is experiencing the fourth industrial revolution, which is based on artificial intelligence, automated and robotic systems in production and management, as well as advancements in nanotechnology, biotechnology, and more.

Thanks to the scientific-technical and industrial revolutions, industry has become the leading sector in the production of material goods and has also had a significant impact on the development of other sectors involved in material goods production.

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